

FACTORS INFLUENCING CAREER CHOICE OF ESPORTS FOR GENERATION Z

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ABSTRACT

Current technological developments, especially in the gaming industry, have created new job opportunities in digital games and a new phenomenon known as e-sports. There is a relationship between e-sports and career. There is still limited research on e-sports and one's career, especially those related to the variables Self-efficacy, Extrinsic Motivation, Intrinsic Motivation, Influence by Third Parties, and Career Exposure, so this study aims to examine more deeply the relationship between these variables and career choices in the z-generation. Two hundred eighty respondents in the Greater Jakarta area were examined using a judgmental sampling technique. This study uses Smartpls 3.0 to test the hypotheses' validity, reliability, and results. The results of the study state that Self-Efficacy, Extrinsic Motivation, Intrinsic Motivation, and Career Exposure affect Career Choice, while Influence by Third Parties does not affect Career Choice.

Keywords: Esport, Career Choice, Generation Z, Gaming Industries, Motivation

INTRODUCTION

The electronic sport or e-sport industry is growing, according to its understanding, namely as a form of sport where electronic devices facilitate the main aspects of this sport, players, teams, and the output of e-sports mediated by computers (Hamari & Sjoblom, 2017; Parshakov, 2017) and have become an evolution of human sports behavior in the current information age (Yue et al., 2020) and has become the popular culture and are widely known by the wider community (McCutcheon et al., 2018). On the other hand, esports also refers to competitive video games where teams or individuals compete against each other (Ramirez et al., 2022). For most gamers, it can be a high-paying job, and a small proportion of them master game skills. It can become esports sponsored by well-known companies (Bányai et al., 2020). E-sport athletes are paid not only by the sponsors who work together but also by the organizations and clubs that oversee the athletes (Nagorski & Widmeyer, 2020). Esport has traditional sports components, such as players, teams, managers, leagues, competitions, events, endorsements, and player transfers. (Jenny, et al., 2017)

Esports is considered the fastest-growing sector in the sports industry today (Nielsen & Karhu Lahti, 2017). In Indonesia alone, up to 52 million people are involved in this industry (Vero, 2022). E-sports has become a source of income for athletes, and Indonesia is ranked 33rd in earning money from esports with a value of \$107,202 (esports earnings, 2022). Enthusiasm for e-sports around the world from 2016 to 2019 continued to increase, supported by the development of the number of e-sports viewers, which is increasing rapidly every year (Haponen & Minashkina, 2019). With the existence of e-sports, it can also lead to new careers

for young people in Indonesia (media Indonesia, 2020), and the Ministry of Youth and Sports and the Indonesian National Sports Committee (KONI) also recognize e-sports as an achievement sport in Indonesia (Saleh, 2020).

Generation Z was born from 1997 to 2012 (Beresford Research, 2019) and was born during a time when technology was advancing rapidly and was easily available. Generation Z makes up quite a large population in Indonesia of 74.93 million people (Central Bureau of Statistics, 2021). Based on data from Lokadata (2018), the gamer population in Indonesia is, on average, 16-24 years old, with the intensity of playing games every day. This has become a new phenomenon where many Z-generations spend their time playing games and plan to get involved in e-sports. For example, one of the e-sports players has earned as much as 49 million dollars from his career in esports this (Esport Earnings, 2021). Like other traditional sports, the average e-sports athlete has been involved in the game world from a young age, namely, 16–20 (Suncho, 2021). The average age of e-sports athletes is very young, from 15 to 25 years old (Martončík, 2015).

Research on e-sports and their relationship with careers still needs to be completed. Most previous studies have discussed the motivations for the consumption of traditional sports and esports (Funk et al., 2017; Lee & Schoenstadt, 2011), watching esports online (Chen & Lin, 2018; Jang et al., 2021; Sjoblom & Hamari, 2017; Hilvert-Bruce et al., 2018), addicted to playing video games (Rumpf et al., 2018; Kiraly et al., 2018; Kim & Park, 2007) and esports with gambling (Rainsbury et al., 2017; Macey & Hamari, 2019).

Career selection is not just a single decision made at one point in time but a process involving many big and small decisions combined to establish one career development trajectory (Ashari, Z., Azman, N., & Rasul, MS, 2019). Several factors influence a person's career choice: self-efficacy, extrinsic motivation, intrinsic motivation, Influenced by Third Parties, and Career exposure (Huang et al., 2018; Ayodele, 2019; Ng et al., 2017). Self-efficacy in career choice refers to individual beliefs to be involved in activities related to choosing a suitable career path (Ogotu, Odera & Maragia., 2017), and people who have confidence in their abilities will have great opportunities to explore their abilities. On the chosen career. In choosing a career, of course, it is important to know information about the career to be chosen. Career Exposure is very important for a person's preferences in choosing their career path (Ng et al., 2017). A person's success in choosing his career path can also be seen from the extrinsic factors that allow a person to work for the expected rewards (Bainbridge, 2015), such as salary, better benefits, and job opportunities. Intrinsic factors are factors that are influenced by personal interests and choices (Jackling & Keneley, 2009), where someone will choose a career just because the field is interesting and makes them confident in getting good results in that career (Odia & Ogie Du, 2013). Influence of third parties, namely support from family, friends, teachers, and career consultants (Ng et al., 2017), participation from third parties is proven effective and supportive, which will ensure one's success in a future career (Meddour et al., 2016).

This research is used to explore what factors can influence someone deciding to make e-sports their career choice. Making e-sports a career is still being debated at this time. Caillois (2001) assumes that competing as a professional gamer has a negative effect because the concept of

the game itself is a free activity. After all, it has playing activities in it, such as (unproductive and fictitious). However, several important elements can categorize esports as any other traditional sport (Thiel & John, 2018). This research is expected to answer the question of what factors influence the choice of e-sport for generation Z.

Theoretical Background and Literature Review

Social Cognitive Career Theory

Social Cognitive Career Theory (SCCT) discusses the variables a person uses to determine his career choice and refers to a person's process in developing his career choices, career interests, and persistence (Lent et al., 1994). Three important variables are used in the career selection process: contextual, attitude, and personal (Flores et al., 2010). SCCT consists of three main principles: self-efficacy, outcome expectations, and goals (Udayanan, 2019). Self-efficacy refers to the belief that a person can successfully perform certain behaviors based on their perceptions of their abilities and their likelihood of success (Bolt Nicky et al., 2018). SCCT argues that self-efficacy and career choices influence one's career choices and goals (Wang et al., 2007). Someone with a high level of self-efficacy also has high expectations of the outcome (Wojcicki, 2009). Goals are influenced by self-efficacy and also outcome expectations. The use of SCCT theory is used because, from previous research, it can help identify factors that influence a career choice (Sheu & Bordon, 2017).

Career Choice

A career is a long road, a goal, and an uphill struggle to pursue that will last a lifetime (Bingol & Cakir, 2021). Career choice can affect a person's future, there needs to be some careful consideration to be able to decide on this career choice finally, and it is important because it will determine a person's success in the next stages of life after leaving the world of education (Harun et al., 2021). A suitable career can determine a person's well-being and life satisfaction, and everyone will have different motivations for a career. Factors that influence a person's decision to have a career in e-sports found that Self-Efficacy, Extrinsic Motivation, Intrinsic Motivation, Influence by third parties, and career exposure are important factors and have a positive influence on someone in choosing a career (Huang et al. al., 2018; Giakoni-Ramirez et al., 2022; Ayodele, 2019; Ng et al., 2017).

Conceptual Definition and Relationship between Variable

Self-Efficacy

Self-efficacy refers to the belief that a person can successfully perform certain behaviors based on their perceptions of their abilities and their likelihood of success in that activity (Blotnicky et al., 2018; Cribbs, Huang & Jimenez, 2021). Individuals with high Self-Efficacy will better understand opportunities for success and can more accurately predict the future (Krueger and Brazeal, 1994 in Qiao and Huang, 2019). Self-efficacy has a considerable impact, not only involving feelings of oneself but also driving success in life; someone who believes in his ability to face future challenges and complete tasks successfully is said to have self-efficacy to succeed (Harun et al., 2021).

Self-efficacy in career choice refers to individual beliefs to engage in activities related to choosing a suitable career path (Ogutu, Odera & Maragia., 2017). Previous research suggests a significant relationship between Self-Efficacy and career choice (Meddour et al., 2016; Huang et al., 2018). Self-Efficacy has a considerable influence that impacts life success. Someone who believes in their ability to face future challenges in their career and can complete tasks successfully has the self-efficacy to succeed (Lent et al., 2017). Thus it can be hypothesized that:

H1: Self-Efficacy has a positive influence on Career Choice of E-sport

Extrinsic Motivation

Extrinsic motivation refers to personal behavior in doing something to achieve a certain goal where the goal is attached to the activity itself (Pelletier et al., 2013; Vallerand et al., 1992; Giakoni-Ramirez et al., 2022) as well as motivation, goals, and learning styles of esports professionals change during the process of becoming professional (Kim & Thomas, 2015). In achieving a goal, extrinsic motivation drives the choice of a career in esports and directs professionals to pursue an award (Banyai et al., 2020; Brock, 2017).

Constructing measurements based on professional understanding can encourage involvement such as career development, career placement, receiving prizes for completing tasks, and reputation to increase individual placement in an e-sport community (Torhonen et al., 2019). Based on the findings of previous studies, it was found that extrinsic motivation has a positive influence on choosing a career (Giakoni-Ramirez et al., 2022; Porter & Woolley, 2014). Thus, it can be hypothesized that:

H2: Extrinsic Motivation has a positive influence on Career Choice of E-sport

Intrinsic Motivation

Intrinsic motivation discusses an activity or something that makes a person feel personally satisfied (Ryan & Deci, 2000). Intrinsic motivation involves interest, pleasure, and satisfaction in doing something (Vansteenkiste et al., 2005). Individuals with high intrinsic motivation tend to show interest and pleasure (Shin & Lee, 2016). Intrinsic motivation also describes a positive experience experienced by someone because they undergo an activity or feel challenged (Ryan & Deci, 2000) but are not influenced by external factors such as pressure, gifts, or coercion from others (Giancola, 2014).

Based on previous research findings, intrinsic motivation has a positive influence on career selection and shows that intrinsic motivation is an important factor in choosing a career (Odia & Ogiedu, 2013). In addition, research on intrinsic motivation factors in choosing a career in the IT field states that intrinsic motivation has a positive influence on choosing a career because of the elements of personal pleasure, challenge, and satisfaction when faced with technology (Potter et al., 2009). Intrinsic factors also positively influence choosing a career (Ayodele, 2019; Panisoara et al., 2013). Thus, it can be hypothesized that:

H3: Intrinsic Motivation has a positive influence on Career Choice of E-sport

Influence by Third Parties

The choice of a career can be influenced by external influences such as other individuals or groups of people such as family members, friends, teachers, or other individuals (Ng et al., 2017; Pablo-Lerchundi et al., 2015; Shumba & Naong, 2012). Students choose the right career path because they seek and receive advice from their parents or family members (Meddour et al., 2016). At the same time, high school teachers or instructors in college have an important role in the final choice of students choosing their business majors (Odia & Ogie Du, 2013), including relatives or friends in the individual's environment (Porter & Woolley, 2014).

Environmental parameters or external influences from individuals, such as support or social level barriers, create a potential influence on career choice positively or negatively as well as directly or indirectly (Lent et al., 2010). Based on previous research findings, it was found that third parties' influence positively influences choosing a career (Ayodele, 2019; Ng et al., 2017; Agarwala, 2008; Nakagomi et al., 2016). Thus, it can be hypothesized that:

H4: Influence by Third Parties has a positive influence on Career Choice of E-sport

Career Exposure

In determining a career, of course, it is necessary to know the nature of the work and what type of career is offered in a field of work. Career Exposure is one of the main considerations in choosing one's career (Ghani et al., 2008). As is known, there are various types of jobs in the e-sport field, such as shout caster, analyst, content creator, event organizer, event administrator, physician, community manager, and the owner (Oliver, 2021). With greater exposure to career-related information, one can make better career choices (Ghani & Said, 2009).

Providing career-related knowledge or information can motivate us to choose a career path in the e-sport field. Previous studies show that career exposure has a positive and significant influence on career choice (Hatane et al., 2021; Ng et al., 2017; Ayodele, 2019). Based on the research results above, career exposure is an important factor in a person's preferences in choosing their career path. Thus, it is hypothesized that:

H5: Career Exposure has a positive influence on Career Choice of E-sport

Figure 1: Literature Mapping

RESEARCH METHOD

The research design in this study is quantitative descriptive type research, which aims to obtain an accurate profile based on an event, the person, or the situation to be studied (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016) in the form of numerical data, and then a conclusion is drawn to reveal a relationship in the study (Albers, 2017; Creswell, 2010). This research was conducted cross-sectionally, where a study was conducted only once in a specified period (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016).

This study uses post-positivism, in which research believes in the truth of a theory even though it is not explained and understood perfectly (Saunders et al., 2019). This study uses primary data, which is collected directly from the main source through surveys, and uses secondary data sources because the data has been collected or processed beforehand (Bairagi & Munot, 2019).

Data Collection Method Data collection

This study used a questionnaire (see appendix 2) online (Google Form), which helps researchers get broad coverage and save time. Respondents' answers were measured using a Likert scale which allows respondents to assess how strongly they agree or disagree with statements (Saunders et al., 2016) related to behavior or objects (Kumar et al., 2018). This scale shows the respondents' assessment of the level of agreement on a series of statements contained in the operational variables and instruments in the study (Maholtra, 2015).

Sampling Method

Individuals in Generation Z interested in choosing a career in e-sports are the subject of choice because they have the characteristics of attention in the scope they want to study (Sugiarto, 2017). The sample is obtained from a list of which members will be taken from the population (Bairagi & Munot, 2019). The sampling technique in this study used non-probability sampling, namely that elements in the population do not have an inherent probability of being selected as sample subjects by judgment sampling, which involves choosing the subject that is placed most advantageously or in the best position to provide the necessary information (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016). Sample size in conducting research Using the rule of 10 times the total indicators in the study (Hair et al., 2011), the indicators in this study were 28. Therefore the sample to be used was 280 respondents (10 x 28 indicators).

Measures

This study aims to determine how individuals want or choose a career in the e-sport industry. Individual elements or attributes in the data collected (Saunders et al., 2016). There are 28 statements for the 5 hypotheses, not including the demographic statement. This study uses a 5-point Likert scale with measurements from Strongly Disagree (1) to Strongly Agree (5) (Saunders et al., 2012) measure all variables used in this study: Self-Efficacy (SE), Extrinsic Motivation (EM), Intrinsic Motivation (IM), Influenced by Third Parties (ITP), Career Exposure (CE), and Career Choice (CC). The measurement items for Self-Efficacy are adapted from Cribbs, Huang & Jimenez (2021) with five statements. Extrinsic and Intrinsic Motivation has 5 statements adapted from Odia & Ogiedu (2013). Influence by Third Parties there are 5 statements adapted from Ng et al. (2017). For Career Exposure, the measurement items are adapted from Dossinger et al. (2019) with 3 statements. Finally, for Career Choice, there are 5

statements which 3 statements are adapted from Ashari, Azman, & Apostle (2019) and 2 from Ng et al. (2017). All variables will be measured using Partial Least Squares-Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) using SmartPLS 3, which is used to analyze data (Ringle et al., 2015). PLS-SEM is also considered suitable for this study because this research is exploratory research, which facilitates the combination of formative indicators and complex models (Hair et al., 2011), and can accommodate a small number of samples (Hair et al., 2019).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on the results of an online survey that was distributed, this study found a total of 280 respondents, most dominant with the age of the respondents at 15 - 17 years with male (68.6%) and female (31.4%) gender, the respondent's domicile dominated by Jakarta (42.9%), while for jobs dominated by students/students by 61.1% followed by not yet working by 22.5% with last education dominated by high school by 59.3%. We also asked respondents about the game genres they participated in and obtained the results of Multiple Online Battle Arena (MOBA) (54.3%) at the top, followed by Battle Royale at 44.3%.

Table 1: Descriptive Statement Results (N=280)

Variable	Total	%	Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Gender			Bogor	26	9.3%
Male	192	68.6%	Depok	50	17.9%
Female	88	31.4%	Tangerang	43	15.4%
Ages			Bekasi	26	9.3%
< 15 Years	0	0%	Outside Greater Jakarta	15	5.4%
15 - 17 Years	125	44.6%	Profession		
18 - 21 Years	97	34.6%	Student	171	61.1%
22 - 25 Years	58	20.7%	Private sector employee	33	11.8%
> 25 Years	0	0%	Businessman	12	4.3%
Last education			Not yet working	63	22.5%
Senior High School	166	59.3%	Other	1	0.4%
D1 - D3	29	10.4%	Game Genre		
S1	64	22.9%	FPS	111	39.9%
S2	19	6.8%	MMORPG	70	25%
Others	2	0.7%	MOBA	152	54.3%
Domicile			Sports	78	27.9%
Jakarta	120	42.9%	Battle Royale	124	44.3%

Before researchers test the 5 existing hypotheses, we will test each indicator item's level of reliability and validity to find the consistency and relationship. We use the Measurement Model, which consists of 3 categories: convergent validity, discriminant validity, and composite reliability (Hair, 2011). Outer models or measurement models are used to evaluate the relationship between indicator variables and existing constructs (Hair et al., 2012) and aim to calculate the reliability, internal consistency, and validity of the variables used (Ho, 2013). Variables that have a loading of 0.7 or greater are considered acceptable (Hair et al., 2011; Forll & Larcker, 1981), and loadings that have a value below 0.7 must be eliminated. Convergent validity values are measured using average variance extracted (AVE) values;

convergent values can be fulfilled if $AVE \geq 0.5$ is found (Henseler et al., 2009). While the reliability test is used to test the consistency and stability of the indicators (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016), and the method used uses Cronbach Alpha, where one variable is considered reliable if Cronbach's Alpha > 0.6 (Malhotra, 2010).

Table 2: Validity and Reliability Test

Variable	Statement	Factor Loading	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability
Self-Efficacy (SE)	SE1. In general, I feel safe trying a career in E-Sport	0.824	0.648	0.819	0.88
	SE2. I'm sure I can do E-Sports career advanced work	0.797			
	SE4. I think I can handle the more difficult E-Sports jobs	0.788			
	SE5. I am very confident in doing things around E-Sport	0.810			
Extrinsic Motivation (EM)	EM1. Having a career in e-sports has a lot of prestige	0.840	0.661	0.872	0.907
	EM2. E-sports is a field with wide business exposure	0.822			
	EM3. A career in e-sports is an honor	0.814			
	EM4. I will earn a lot of money if I have a career in e-sports	0.780			
	EM5. I choose a career in e-sports because of the many opportunities available	0.809			
Intrinsic Motivation (IM)	IM1. I like the e-sports industry	0.792	0.636	0.857	0.897
	IM2. E-sports are interesting	0.768			
	IM3. I will enjoy a career in e-sports	0.841			
	IM4. I am willing to spend time learning e-sports	0.807			
	IM5. I can do e-sport activities better	0.779			
Influenced by Third Parties (ITP)	ITP1. My family and friends have an influence on the decision to choose a career in e-sports	0.819	0.662	0.830	0.887
	ITP2. I am influenced by educators in choosing a career in e-sports	0.799			

	ITP4. I am influenced by the public/community in choosing a career in e-sports	0.831			
	ITP5. I was influenced by career counselors in choosing a career in e-sports	0.806			
Career Exposure (CE)	CE1. People around me, Teachers, Parents, Friends or individuals around you give or recommend you to choose a career in E-Sport	0.883	0.719	0.804	0.884
	CE2. People around me, Teachers, Parents, Friends or individuals around you give or recommend you to improve a career in the field of E-Sports.	0.822			
	CE3. People around me, Teachers, Parents, Friends or individuals around you give or recommend you to choose a job in the field of E-Sports that can help you meet new colleagues.	0.837			
Career Choice (CC)	CC1. I will choose a career in E-Sports.	0.820	0.636	0.856	0.897
	CC2. It is important to consider my abilities when choosing a career in E-Sports.	0.796			
	CC3. A career in E-Sports will be my priority when choosing a career.	0.802			
	CC4. I have the intention to pursue a professional qualification in the field of E-Sports.	0.727			
	CC5. I clearly know the career options in E-Sports that are available to me.	0.839			

Based on table 1, 2 variables are declared inappropriate or invalid for use in research, namely the SE3 variable with a factor loading value of 0.699 and the ITP 3 variable with a factor loading value of 0.445, so we eliminated these two variables. For other variables, it is declared feasible or valid for research use and can be used for further analysis because the results of factor loading > 0.7 . Based on the 28 indicators in table 2, Cronbach alpha meets the requirements where each existing indicator results above 0.6 to be reliable. While the results

of the AVE test for each indicator have been declared valid because the results obtained are ≥ 0.5 .

Table 3: Discriminant Validity

	Career Choice	Career Exposure	Extrinsic Motivation	Intrinsic Motivation	Influenced by Third Parties	Self Efficacy
Career Choice	0.798					
Career Exposure	0.820	0.848				
Extrinsic Motivation	0.853	0.785	0.813			
Intrinsic Motivation	0.872	0.815	0.849	0.798		
Influenced by Third Parties	0.810	0.813	0.804	0.816	0.814	
Self-Efficacy	0.835	0.809	0.844	0.832	0.807	0.805

The results of the convergent validity and reliability tests are in table 2, while the results of the discriminant validity tests are presented in table 3. Based on table 3, namely discriminant validity, it can be concluded that each variable that has been tested has been fulfilled. This can be fulfilled if the results of each variable tested have obtained the above results from the AVE tested in table 2, where the AVE provisions obtained results ≥ 0.5 . After testing the outer model, we tested the inner model, which consisted of the R-Square Test (R2), Q-Square Test (Q2), and Hypothesis Test (Path Coefficient).

Table 4: Coefficient of Determination (R2) Testing Results

Variable	R Square	Adjusted R Square
Career Choice (CC)	0.830	0.827

Based on table 4, the R Square value is 0.830, where the results are considered good because if a result of 0.67 is considered good, a result of 0.33 is considered moderate, while a result of 0.19 is considered not good (Ghozali, 2014). The adjusted R Square value of this research is 0.827 and then converted into percent form, which means that self-efficacy, extrinsic motivation, intrinsic motivation, influence by third parties, and career exposure have a combined effect of 82.7%, and the remaining 17.3 % is influenced by other factors not explained in this study. On the other hand, if the R-Square results are close to 1 (one), it can be said that the independent variable can predict the dependent variable very well.

Table 5: Q-Square (Q2) Testing Results

Variable	Q-Square
Career Choice (CC)	0.516

Predictive relevance or Q-Square value (Q²) has the objective of measuring how well the research value is carried out by the model and its parameters (Ghozali, 2016), and can be obtained using a blindfolding procedure, then applied to the variables to be tested with reflective measurements (Ghozali 2012; Hair et al., 2011). Based on table 5, it can be concluded that the indicators or constructs used have strong predictive relevance. This is because the Q-

Square value is 0.516, which is considered sufficient if it shows a result of more than 0.35 (Latan and Ghazali, 2012), and a Q-Square that is greater than 0 (zero) indicates a predictive relevance value (Hair et al., 2011; Chin, 2010).

Table 6: Hypothesis Testing Results

	Hypothesis	Path Coefficients	T - Statistic	P - Values	Result
H1	SE → CC	0.139	2.090	0.037	Supported
H2	EM → CC	0.247	3.201	0.001	Supported
H3	IM → CC	0.341	3.593	0.000	Supported
H4	ITP → CC	0.088	1.344	0.180	Not Supported
H5	CE → CC	0.165	2.228	0.026	Supported

This study uses a significance level of 5% with a confidence level of 95%. The value of the t-statistic must exceed the number > 1.96 with a significance value of < 0.05 (Hair et al., 2011), so it can be concluded that the hypothesis has a significant effect. The hypothesis is insignificant if the t-statistic is less than < 1.96 (Haryono, 2017). As seen in table 4 above, it can be seen that hypotheses 1, 2, 3, and 5 are fulfilled with the t-statistic criteria > 1.96 and p-value < 0.05 . Meanwhile, hypothesis 4 (H4), with a p-value of 0.180 and a t-statistic of 1.344, is not supported because the p-value > 0.05 and the t-statistic value < 1.96 . This is supported by previous research, which also says that the effect influence of third parties has no effect or has less influence on career selection (Wally, 2013; Odia & Ogiedu, 2013; Ng et al., 2017). With Generation Z, already born with quite advanced technology, influence from third parties such as family, colleagues, friends or others is considered less influential. This can be said because Generation Z can better understand and feel about technology themselves. Therefore, if they like the e-sport industry based on their wishes, then the influence of third parties does not play a role in choosing their career. Self-efficacy is one of the important things in determining a career, especially for Generation-Z. If their preferences are following the work to be occupied later, it will positively impact their future careers. Based on the results of hypothesis testing (H1) accepted, this is in line with previous research, which also said that self-efficacy is one of the references for individuals in choosing a career (Meddour et al., 2016; Huang et al., 2018). In the inherent personality of Generation-Z, the confidence in their ability to choose a career will be an advantage for them. If they already have this, it will be a reference if Generation-Z has the esports industry as their future career. Furthermore, extrinsic motivation can encourage Generation Z to choose a career they will choose later. This can be seen from the jobs available in the esports industry and the income they will get from carrying out that career. The second hypothesis (H2) is accepted, in line with previous research that extrinsic motivation has a positive influence on career selection, Peter & Wooley (2014) which states that extrinsic factors such as income and career stability are an encouragement to choose a career. Generation Z has high external motivation for choosing e-sports as their career path because they tend to see successful people in the e-sports industry.

Motivation in each individual in an activity that they carry out will encourage them to have a sense of personal satisfaction. Suppose the individual is more interested and happy about the activity being carried out or will be carried out. In that case, the individual will get a positive experience in carrying out the activity. Based on the results of the hypothesis test (H3), it is accepted that this is in line with previous research, which also says that intrinsic motivation has

a positive influence on career choice (Ayodele, 2019; Ng et al., 2017; Agarwala, 2008; Nakagomi et al., 2016). Therefore, if Generation Z is motivated by the esports industry or enjoys playing games (Kiraly et al., 2018; Kim & Park, 2007) and wants to become a professional in the esports industry, they will be able to support these individuals in choosing a career in the esports industry in the future. It is known that the career path in the esports field is quite good and has been supported by the government by developing the e-sport ecosystem in Indonesia as an outstanding sport (Faiton, 2021). The higher the development of esports in Indonesia, the more types of jobs are available in the esports field, such as shoutcaster, analyst, content creator, event organizer, event administrator, physician, community manager, the owner (Oliver, 2021) and success in their careers also makes Generations considerations -Z in choosing a career. Berdasarkan hasil uji hipotesis (H4) diterima, hal ini sejalan dengan penelitian sebelumnya bahwa Career Exposure memiliki pengaruh yang positif terhadap Career Choice (Hatane et al., 2021 ; Ng et al., 2017; Ayodele, 2019). The explanation above makes Career Exposure one of Generation Z's considerations in determining a career.

CONCLUSION AND MANAGERIAL IMPLICATIONS

Overall, this study discusses the factors that influence the Z-generation, such as Self-Efficacy, Extrinsic Motivation, Intrinsic Motivation, Influenced by Third Parties, and Career Exposure to Career Choice. Based on the results of this study, 4 hypotheses were accepted, and 1 other hypothesis was rejected. Based on the hypothesis testing, Self-Efficacy, Extrinsic Motivation, Intrinsic Motivation, and Career Exposure significantly influence Career Choice. In contrast, being influenced by Third Parties negatively influences Career Choice. This research can be useful for education providers, especially educational institutions, to prepare new academic learning, namely esports, because they see the huge potential of the esports industry and also have a growing market. So, Z-generation or later generations can prepare themselves to enter the esports industry and can be profitable for students and education providers. As a professional player, many derivative branches of e-sports can be utilized by education providers, such as shoutcasters, analysts, esports management, and esports organizers.

LIMITATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

The limitation of this study is that there is a gap in the gender of the respondents, where most of the respondents who filled out were men (68.6%). So, the next study can use equal respondents between men and women. Due to the dominance of male respondents and usually in the world of e-sports, there are still many men, and we can provide recommendations for further research to examine further the role of women in the world of e-sports or gender comparison, which can be another factor in choosing esports as a career in the future. Next, the number of samples used in this study is at a minimum value to represent a population. However, it is better to increase the number of respondents distributed to obtain more valid results in measuring each indicator. Lastly, the respondents of this study are generation Z, who live in Indonesia, thus illustrating the research context in Indonesia. For the next study, similar research can be conducted in different countries to fully understand what factors influence the Z-generation in choosing a career in e-sports. Even though this research is still being carried out in Indonesia, further research that has research respondents, namely students outside

Indonesia who chooses academic esports, can use this research as a reference. Individual motivation in playing games can also be one of the reasons why if individuals play games, they can run them professionally and improve their skills. Therefore, in future research, it can be one indicator for further research.

References

- Agarwala, T. (2008). Factors influencing career choice of management students in India. *Career Development International*.
- Albers, M. J. (2017). Quantitative data analysis—In the graduate curriculum. *Journal of Technical Writing and Communication*, 47(2), 215-233.
- Ashari, Z. H. M., Azman, N., & Rasul, M. S. (2019). Factors predicting career choice among Malaysian students in skills-based training institutions. *International Journal for Educational and Vocational Guidance*, 19(1), 19-39.
- Ayodele, T. O. (2019). Career choice of real estate students in Nigeria: The explaining influences in comparative perspective. *Property Management*.
- Badan Pusat Statistik Indonesia (2021). Hasil Sensus Penduduk 2020. Jakarta: Indonesia
- Bainbridge, C. 2015. What is extrinsic motivation? AboutParenting. Available from: <http://giftedkids.about.com/od/glossary/g/extrinsic.htm> [Assessed 7 March 2015].
- Bairagi, V., & Munot, M. V. (Eds.). (2019). *Research methodology: A practical and scientific approach*. CRC Press.
- Bányai, F., Zsila, Á., Griffiths, M. D., Demetrovics, Z., & Király, O. (2020). Career as a professional gamer: Gaming motives as predictors of career plans to become a professional esports player. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 1866.
- Beresford Research. (2022). Generations defined by name, birth year, and ages in 2022. Retrieved from: <https://www.beresfordresearch.com/age-range-by-generation/>
- Bingöl, U., & Çakir, Y. N. (2021). Impact of Future Expectations on Career Planning Attitudes' of Professional Esports Athletes. *Yönetim Bilimleri Dergisi*, 19(39), 203-224.
- Blotnicky, K. A., Franz-Odenaal, T., French, F., & Joy, P. (2018). A study of the correlation between STEM career knowledge, mathematics self-efficacy, career interests, and career activities on the likelihood of pursuing a STEM career among middle school students. *International journal of STEM education*, 5(1), 1-15.
- Brock, T. (2017). Roger Caillois and e-sports: On the problems of treating play as work. *Games and Culture*, 12(4), 321-339.
- Caillois, R. (2001). *Man, Play and Games*. Chicago, IL: University of Illinois Press.
- Chen, C. C., & Lin, Y. C. (2018). What drives live-stream usage intention? The perspectives of flow, entertainment, social interaction, and endorsement. *Telematics and Informatics*, 35(1), 293-303.
- Chin, W. W. (2010). Bootstrap cross-validation indices for PLS path model assessment. In *Handbook of partial least squares* (pp. 83-97). Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg.
- Creswell John, W. (2010). *Research Design Pendekatan Kualitatif, Kuantitatif, dan Mixed*. Achmad Fawaid, penerjemah. Yogyakarta (ID): Pustaka Belajar. Terjemahan dari: *Research Design Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches*, Ed ke-3.

- Cribbs, J., Huang, X., & Piatek-Jimenez, K. (2021). Relations of mathematics mindset, mathematics anxiety, mathematics identity, and mathematics self-efficacy to STEM career choice: A structural equation modeling approach. *School Science and Mathematics*, 121(5), 275-287.
- Dossinger, Karyn; Wanberg, Connie R.; Choi, Yongjun; Leslie, Lisa M. (2019). The beauty premium: The role of organizational sponsorship in the relationship between physical attractiveness and early career salaries. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, (), S0001879119300247.
- Esports Earnings (2021). Highest Earnings By Age. Retrieved from: esportsearnings.com
- Faiton, N. (2021). Piala Presiden Esports 2021 Bangun Jenjang Karir Atlet Esports & Prestasi Bangsa. Retrieved from antvklik.com.
- Flores, L. Y., Robitschek, C., Celebi, E., Andersen, C., & Hoang, U. (2010). Social cognitive influences on Mexican Americans' career choices across Holland's themes. *Journal of vocational behavior*, 76(2), 198-210.
- Funk, Daniel C.; Pizzo, Anthony D.; Baker, Bradley J. (2017). eSport management: Embracing eSport education and research opportunities. *Sport Management Review*,()
- FORNLL, C., & Larcker, D. (1981). Structural equation models with unobservable variables and measurement error.
- Gainsbury, S. M., Abarbanel, B., & Blaszczyński, A. (2017). Game on: Comparison of demographic profiles, consumption behaviors, and gambling site selection criteria of esports and sports bettors. *Gaming Law Review*, 21(8), 575-587.
- Geoghegan, L.; Wormald, J.C.R. Sport-Related Hand Injury: A New Perspective of e-Sports. *J. Hand Surg. Eur. Vol.* 2019, 44, 219–220.
- Ghani, E.K., Said, J., Nasir, N.M. and Jusoff, K. (2008), "The 21st century accounting career from the perspective of the Malaysian University students", *Asian Social Science*, Vol. 4 No. 8, pp. 73-83.
- Ghani, E. K., & Said, J. 2009. A comparative study on Malay and Chinese accounting students' perceptions on accounting career. *Canadian Social Science*, 5(3): 1-13.
- Ghozali, I. (2016) *Aplikasi Analisis Multivariate Dengan Program IBM SPSS 23*. Edisi 8. Semarang: Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro.
- Ghozali, Imam. 2014. *Structural Equation Modeling, Metode Alternatif dengan Partial Least Square (PLS)*. Edisi 4. Semarang : Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro.
- Giakoni-Ramírez, F., Merellano-Navarro, E., & Duclos-Bastías, D. (2022). Professional Esports Players: Motivation and Physical Activity Levels. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(4), 2256.
- Giancola, F. L. (2014). Should HR professionals devote more time to intrinsic rewards?. *Compensation & Benefits Review*, 46(1), 25-31.
- Hair, J. F., Ringle, C. M., & Sarstedt, M. (2011). PLS-SEM: Indeed a silver bullet. *Journal of Marketing theory and Practice*, 19(2), 139-152.
- Hair, J. F., Sarstedt, M., Pieper, T. M., & Ringle, C. M. (2012). The use of partial least squares structural equation modeling in strategic management research: a review of past practices and recommendations for future applications. *Long range planning*, 45(5-6), 320-340.
- Hair, J. F., Sarstedt, M., & Ringle, C. M. (2019). Rethinking some of the rethinking of partial least squares. *European Journal of Marketing*, 53(4), 566–584.
- Hallmann, K., & Giel, T. (2018). eSports—Competitive sports or recreational activity?. *Sport management review*, 21(1), 14-20.

- Hamari, J., & Sjöblom, M. (2017). What is eSports and why do people watch it?. Internet research.
- Happonen, A., & Minashkina, D. (2019). Professionalism in esports: benefits in skills and health & possible downsides.
- Harun¹, S., Abd Rahman, M. B., & Abd Rahman, R. (2021). Factors Influencing Career Adaptability and Vocational Employability Towards Career Choice Among Bakery and Pastry Students.
- Haryono, S. (2017). Metode SEM untuk penelitian manajemen AMOS, LISREL. PLS. PT. Luxima Metro Media.
- Hatane, S. E., Gunawan, F. A., & Pratama, S. W. (2021). Intrinsic motivation, career exposure, and quality of life: How do they influence the accounting students' career choice? *Journal of Education and Learning (EduLearn)*.
- Henseler, J., Ringle, C. M., & Sinkovics, R. R. (2009). The use of partial least squares path modeling in international marketing. In *New challenges to international marketing*. Emerald Group Publishing Limited.
- Hilvert-Bruce, Z., Neill, J. T., Sjöblom, M., & Hamari, J. (2018). Social motivations of live-streaming viewer engagement on Twitch. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 84, 58-67.
- Ho, R. (2013). *Handbook of univariate and multivariate data analysis with IBM SPSS*. CRC press.
- Huang, X., Zhang, J., & Hudson, L. (2019). Impact of math self-efficacy, math anxiety, and growth mindset on math and science career interest for middle school students: the gender moderating effect. *European Journal of Psychology of Education*, 34(3), 621-640.
- Hulin, C. L., Drasgow, F., & Parsons, C. K. (1983). *Item response theory: Application to psychological measurement*. Dorsey Press.
- Jackling, B., & Keneley, M. 2009. Influences on the supply of accounting graduates in Australia: A focus on international students. *Accounting & Finance*, 49: 141-159.
- Jang, W. W., Byon, K. K., Baker III, T. A., & Tsuji, Y. (2020). Mediating effect of esports content live streaming in the relationship between esports recreational gameplay and esports event broadcast. *Sport, Business and Management: An International Journal*.
- Jenny, S. E., Manning, R. D., Keiper, M. C., & Olrich, T. W. (2017). Virtual (ly) athletes: where eSports fit within the definition of "Sport". *Quest*, 69(1), 1-18.
- Karhulahti, V.-M. Reconsidering Esport: Economics and Executive Ownership. *Phys. Cult. Sport. Stud. Res.* 2017, 74, 43–53.
- Király, O., Griffiths, M. D., King, D. L., Lee, H. K., Lee, S. Y., Bányai, F., ... & Demetrovics, Z. (2018). Policy responses to problematic video game use: A systematic review of current measures and future possibilities. *Journal of Behavioral Addictions*, 7(3), 503-517.
- Kim, S. H., and Thomas, M. K. (2015). A stage theory model of professional video game players in South Korea: the socio-cultural dimensions of the development of expertise. *Asian J. Inform. Technol.* 14, 176–186.
- Kim, Y. E., & Park, S. H. (2007). A study on the online game use influences in game flow and addiction: Focusing on the uses and gratifications approach. *Korean Journal of Journalism and Communication Studies*, 51(1), 355-377.
- Krueger Jr, N. F., & Brazeal, D. V. (1994). Entrepreneurial potential and potential entrepreneurs. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 18(3), 91-104.
- Kumar, V., Leone, R. P., Aaker, D. A., & Day, G. S. (2018). *Marketing research*. John Wiley & Sons.

- Latan, H., & Ghozali, I. (2012). *Partial Least Square: Konsep, Teknik, dan Aplikasi SmartPLS 2.0 M3*. Semarang: Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro.
- Lee, D., & Schoenstedt, L. J. (2011). Comparison of eSports and traditional sports consumption motives. *ICHPER-SD Journal Of Research*, 6(2), 39-44.
- Lent, R. W., Brown, S. D., & Hackett, G. (1994). Toward a unifying social cognitive theory of career and academic interest, choice, and performance. *Journal of vocational behavior*, 45(1), 79-122.
- Lent, R. W., Ireland, G. W., Penn, L. T., Morris, T. R., & Sappington, R. (2017). Sources of self-efficacy and outcome expectations for career exploration and decision-making: A test of the social cognitive model of career self-management. *Journal of vocational behavior*, 99, 107-117.
- Lent, R.W., Paixão, M.P., Da Silva, J.T. and Leitão, L.M. (2010), "Predicting occupational interests and choice aspirations in Portuguese high school students: a test of social cognitive career theory", *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, Vol. 76 No. 2, pp. 244-251.
- Lokadata. (2018). Pemain game menurut usia, 2018. Retrieved from: <https://lokadata.beritagar.id/chart/preview/pemain-game-online-menurut-usia-2018-1579509362>
- Macey, J., & Hamari, J. (2019). eSports, skins and loot boxes: Participants, practices and problematic behaviour associated with emergent forms of gambling. *New Media & Society*, 21(1), 20-41.
- Macey, J., Tyrväinen, V., Pirkkalainen, H., & Hamari, J. (2020). Does esports spectating influence game consumption?. *Behaviour & Information Technology*, 1-17.
- Malhotra, N. K. (2010). *Riset Pemasaran (Marketing Research)(Edisi 4 Jilid 1)*. New Jersey, Indonesia: PT. Indeks.
- Martončík, M. (2015). e-Sports: Playing just for fun or playing to satisfy life goals?. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 48, 208-211.
- McCutcheon, C., Hitchens, M., & Drachen, A. (2017, December). eSport vs irlSport. In the *International Conference on Advances in Computer Entertainment* (pp. 531-542). Springer, Cham.
- Meddour, H., Abdo, A. A., Majid, A. H., Auf, M. A., & Aman, A. M. (2016). Factors Affecting Career Choice Among Undergraduate Students in Universitas Indonesia. *International Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 10(4).
- Media Indonesia (2020). Industri E-sport Tumbuhkan Ekonomi dan Serap Tenaga Kerja. Retrieved from: mediaindonesia.com
- Mundfrom, Daniel J., Dale G. Shaw, and Tian Lu Ke. "Minimum sample size recommendations for conducting factor analyses." *International journal of testing* 5, no. 2 (2005): 159-168.
- Nagorsky, E., & Wiemeyer, J. (2020). The structure of performance and training in esports. *PloS one*, 15(8), e0237584.
- Nakagomi, K., Hayashi, Y., & Komiyama, T. (2016). Survey of attitudes toward career choice among pharmacy students at a private university. *Pharmacy Education*, 16.
- Ng, Y. H., Lai, S. P., Su, Z. P., Yap, J. Y., Teoh, H. Q., & Lee, H. (2017). Factors influencing accounting students' career paths. *Journal of Management Development*.
- Nielsen, R. K. L., & Karhulahti, V. M. (2017, August). The problematic coexistence of" internet gaming disorder" and esports. In *Proceedings of the 12th International Conference on the Foundations of Digital Games* (pp. 1-4).
- Odia, J. O., & Ogiedu, K. O. (2013). Factors affecting the study of accounting in Nigerian Universities. *Journal of Educational and Social Research*, 3(3), 89-89.

- Oliver, A. (2021). Mengenal Ekosistem Industri Esport dan Prospek Karier di Dalamnya. Retrieved from Glints: <https://glints.com/id/lowongan/mengenal-pekerjaan-industri-esport/#.Yl6J8OhBxPZ>
- Ogutu, J. P., Odera, P., & Maragia, S. N. (2017). Self-Efficacy as a Predictor of Career Decision Making among Secondary School Students in Busia County, Kenya. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 8(11), 20-29.
- Pablo-Lerchundi, I., Morales-Alonso, M. and González-Tirados, R.M. (2015), “Influences of parental occupation on occupational choices and professional values”, *Journal of Business Research*, Vol. 68 No. 7, pp. 1645-1649.
- Pânisora, G., Pânisora, I.O., Lupascu, A. and Negovan, V. (2013), “Motivation for career in teenagers”, *Procedia – Social and Behavioral Sciences*, Vol. 78, May, pp. 100-104.
- Parshakov, P., Naidenova, I., & Barajas, A. (2020). Spillover effect in promotion: Evidence from video game publishers and eSports tournaments. *Journal of Business Research*, 118, 262-270.
- Pelletier, L. G., Rocchi, M. A., Vallerand, R. J., Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (2013). Validation of the revised sport motivation scale (SMS-II). *Psychology of sport and exercise*, 14(3), 329-341.
- Porter, J., & Woolley, D. (2014). An examination of the factors affecting students’ decision to major in accounting. *International Journal of Accounting and Taxation*, 2(4), 1-22.
- Potter, L. E. C., von Hellens, L. A., & Nielsen, S. H. (2009). Childhood Interest in IT and the Choice of IT as a Career: The Experiences of a Group of IT Professionals. In Proceedings of the special interest group on management information system's 47th annual conference on Computer personnel research (pp. 33-40).
- Qiao, X., & Huang, J. H. (2019). Effect of college students’ entrepreneurial self-efficacy on entrepreneurial intention: career adaptability as a mediating variable. *International Journal of Educational Methodology*, 5(3), 305-313.
- Ryan, R. M., & Deci, E. L. (2000). Intrinsic and extrinsic motivations: Classic definitions and new directions. *Contemporary educational psychology*, 25(1), 54-67.
- Ringle, C. M., Wende, S., & Becker, J. M. (2015). *SmartPLS 3*. SmartPLS GmbH. Bönningstedt, Germany.
- Roscoe, J. T. (1975). *Fundamental research statistics for the behavioral sciences* (Second ed.). New York: Holt Rinehart and Winston.
- Rumpf, H. J., Achab, S., Billieux, J., Bowden-Jones, H., Carragher, N., Demetrovics, Z., ... & Poznyak, V. (2018). Including gaming disorder in the ICD-11: The need to do so from a clinical and public health perspective: Commentary on: A weak scientific basis for gaming disorder: Let us err on the side of caution (van Rooij et al., 2018). *Journal of behavioral addictions*, 7(3), 556-561.
- Saleh, Nurdin. (2020). Esports Sudah Resmi Diakui KONI sebagai Cabang Olahraga Prestasi. Retrieved from: <https://sport.tempo.co/read/1380552/esports-sudah-resmi-diakui-koni-sebagai-cabang-olahraga-prestasi/full&view=ok>
- Saunders, M, Lewis, P & Thornhill H. (2016). Seventh edition *Research Methods for Business Student*. Munich : Pearson.
- Saunders, M., Lewis, P. & Thornhill, A. (2019). *Research Methods for Business Students Ebook*. United Kingdom: Pearson Education.
- Sekaran, U., & Bougie, R. (2016). *Research Methods for Business A Skill Building Approach*. United Kingdom: John Wiley & Sons.
- Sheu, H. B., & Bordon, J. J. (2017). SCCT research in the international context: Empirical evidence, future directions, and practical implications. *Journal of Career Assessment*, 25(1), 58-74.

- Shin, Y. J., & Lee, J. Y. (2017). Attachment, career-choice pessimism, and intrinsic motivation as predictors of college students' career adaptability. *Journal of Career Development*, 44(4), 311-326.
- Shumba, A. and Naong, M. (2012), "Factors influencing students' career choice and aspirations in South Africa", *Journal of Social Science*, Vol. 33 No. 2, pp. 169-178.
- Sjöblom, M., & Hamari, J. (2017). Why do people watch others play video games? An empirical study on the motivations of Twitch users. *Computers in human behavior*, 75, 985-996.
- Sjöblom, M., M. Törhönen, J. Hamari, and J. Macey. (2019). "The Ingredients of Twitch Streaming: Affordances of Game Streams." *Computers in Human Behavior* 92: 20–28.
- Sugiarto. (2017). *Metode Penelitian Bisnis*. Yogyakarta: Andi.
- Suncho, Seth. (2020). What is an eSports Gamer's Career Length? [and Why do Most Retire Early?]. Retrieved from: <https://esportslane.com/esports-gamer-career-length/>
- Thiel, A., & John, J. M. (2018). Is eSport a 'real' sport? Reflections on the spread of virtual competitions. *European Journal for Sport and Society*, 15(4), 311-315.
- Törhönen, M., Sjöblom, M., Hassan, L., & Hamari, J. (2019). Fame and fortune, or just fun? A study on why people create content on video platforms. *Internet Research*.
- Udayanan, P. (2019). The role of self-efficacy and entrepreneurial self-efficacy on the entrepreneurial intentions of graduate students: A study among omani graduates. *Entrepreneurial Business and Economics Review*, 7(4), 7-20.
- Vallerand, R. J., & Blssonnette, R. (1992). Intrinsic, extrinsic, and amotivational styles as predictors of behavior: A prospective study. *Journal of personality*, 60(3), 599-620.
- Vansteenkiste, M., Zhou, M., Lens, W., & Soenens, B. (2005). Experiences of autonomy and control among Chinese learners: Vitalizing or immobilizing?. *Journal of educational psychology*, 97(3), 468.
- Vero (2022). *Gaming & Esports in Indonesia: Highlighting Opportunities for Brands*.
- Wally, L., B. (2013). Factors influencing students' choice of accounting as a major: The case of Botswana accounting students. *Asian Journal of Empirical Research*, 3(4): 464-476.
- Wang, C., Lo, Y. Y., Xu, Y., Wang, Y., & Porfeli, E. (2007). Constructing the search for a job in academia from the perspectives of self-regulated learning strategies and social cognitive career theory. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 70(3), 574-589.
- Wójcicki, T. R., White, S. M., & McAuley, E. (2009). Assessing outcome expectations in older adults: the multidimensional outcome expectations for exercise scale. *The journals of gerontology. Series B, Psychological sciences and social sciences*, 64(1), 33–40.
- Xiaoping, Q. Í. A. O., & Hua, J. H. (2019). Effect of college students' entrepreneurial self-efficacy on entrepreneurial intention: career adaptability as a mediating variable. *International Journal of Educational Methodology*, 5(3), 305-313.
- Yue, Y., Rui, W., & Ling, S. C. S. (2020). Development of E-sports industry in China: Current situation, Trend and research hotspot. *International Journal of Esports*, 1(1).